

FATIGUE BEHAVIOUR OF COMPOSITE JOINTS WITH HEXAGON BOLTS

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SUMMARY: An experimental fatigue program was carried out on composite joints with titanium bolts. Single, double, and triple-row double lap joints were tested in cyclic loading with the stress ratio, $R = -1$. In order to study the development of fatigue damage in the joints bolt movement, relative displacement between composite plates, and strain gauge measurements were used. Fatigue tests have shown that the fatigue resistance of multirow joints is better than that of single-row joints. Direct measurements of damage development showed a significant influence of reduction in the pre-stress in the bolts and fatigue degradation of the bolt holes on relative displacement between composite plates and bolt movement. There was a significant effect on the strain evolution from the bolts during fatigue loading.

KEYWORDS: Bolted Joints, Fatigue, Bolt movement, Strain

INTRODUCTION

Advanced composite materials are experiencing increasing use in the aerospace industry because of their high strength-to-weight and stiffness-to-weight ratios. In aircraft structures the load between different parts is transferred by mechanically fastened or bonded joints. In comparison with adhesive joining, mechanical joints are used in cases when thick laminates have to be joined, when there is a requirement for different parts of the same structure to be disassembled for inspection, or repair purposes. However, bolt holes are a stress concentration factor in the composite joint plates, which could significantly reduced the mechanical performance of joined structures. On the other hand, aircraft structures experience a vast spectrum of extreme service conditions that include the presence of fatigue loading. The certification of aircraft requires that aircraft components manufactured from composite materials be able to withstand the presence of fatigue loading in service [1–3]. Therefore, it would seem that the fatigue behaviour of composite joints plays an important role in the design and performance of aircraft composite structures.

As previous investigations have shown, bolt movement is an important part of the overall behaviour of composite bolted joints. However, only few methods of bolt-movement measurement, such as the use of a potentiometer transducer, a low-kilovolt radiography, and shadow moire techniques, have been mentioned in the published literature [4–6]. Since most of them are quite complicated to mount and use, new simple techniques are needed in order to observe processes associated with the bolt/composite

interface. According to Ref. [7], the presence of fasteners have an influence on the evolution of strain between them under loading. Therefore, it may be of interest to study this effect involving strain gauge measurements during fatigue tests.

As it would seem, more experimental data and some development in experimental methods are required to understand more deeply the fatigue behaviour of composite bolted joints in order to improve the total mechanical performance of composite structures containing bolted connections.

The objective of this investigation is to obtain experimental results on the fatigue behaviour of composite joints with different configuration and geometry. Strain gauge measurements are to be carried out between bolt rows during fatigue tests. Bolt-movement measurements are to be done to analyse the fatigue process in the bolt/composite interface. Relative displacement between the joint plates is to be measured using extensometers.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Specimen plates were manufactured from carbon fibre/epoxy material system (HTA7/6376). A quasi-isotropic lay-up, $(45/0/90)_{3s}$ and $(45/0/90)_{6s}$, was used for outer and middle plates. The composite plates were joined by two, four, and six titanium Hexagon bolts as shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1: Specimens tested in fatigue.

The nominal bolt diameter was 6 mm. This gives the following geometric ratio of the laminate strip width, edge distance and thickness to the bolt diameter: $w/d = 4.5$, $e/d = 2.5$, and $t/d = 1.04$. The Hexagon bolts were tightened to a torque of 9 Nm.

Strain gauges were applied on some of the double lap joints in order to measure strain between different bolt rows. Figure 2 shows the locations of the strain gauges on the specimen surface. The strain gauges were glued on one of the outer plates.

Fig. 2: Strain gauge positions on the specimen surface with four and six bolts.

In order to measure relative displacement between two composite plates, extensometers were used as shown in Fig. 3(a).

Fig. 3: Application of extensometers: (a) for relative displacement measurements between composite plates; (b) for bolt-movement measurements.

To measure bolt movement, a special fixture was built and attached together with an extensometer to the specimen as shown in Fig. 3(b).

The specimens were fatigue tested at different load levels with the stress ratio, $R = \sigma_{min}/\sigma_{max}$, equal to -1. An aluminium lateral support was used to prevent buckling of the joints as shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4: The testing machine grips with the specimen and test fixture.

The specimen plates and the lateral support were interleaved with Teflon sheets to decrease the friction force between the composite plates and the fixture set-up. All fatigue tests were performed under the load control mode of the testing machine to assure that a constant maximum and minimum alternating load will be applied to the specimen. The testing machine was set to stop cyclic loading when the grip-displacement limit was reached and fatigue failure was thus assumed to have occurred. This limit was determined by adding 0.8 mm to the total deflection magnitude of the specimen during fatigue loading. The deflection was monitored using an IBM PC. The bolt temperature was measured to make sure heating did not occur in specimen. The maximum temperature limit was set to +33°C. If heating occurred the frequency of the test was reduced. All experiments were performed at room temperature ($\approx 22^\circ\text{C}$) and ambient relative humidity ($\approx 65\%$).

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Fatigue resistance of the joints

The fatigue test results are presented in Fig. 5 together with the ultimate tensile strength and strain for each joint configuration taken from [7]. The lines in the plots are from least squares fit to the logarithmic fatigue data.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 5: Fatigue test results.

As seen, the joints with six bolts performed the highest resistance to fatigue, followed by the joints with four bolts. The lowest fatigue resistance was shown by the joint with two bolts.

In most of the fatigue tests, failure of the specimens occurred because of fatigue failure of fasteners. The specimens with two bolts failed after one bolt broke (see Fig. 6(a)); whereas the joints with four and six bolts failed after at least two fasteners fractured (see Fig. 6(b) and (c)).

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Fig. 6: Fatigue tested joints.

Specimens with six bolts, tested at $\sigma = 275$ MPa and higher load levels, failed either due to net-section failure occurred or due to fatigue failure of bolts followed by net-section failure (see Fig. 6(d)). It is believed that after the fracture of bolts the net-section transferred more load. This eventually resulted in net-section secondary failure mode.

Relative displacement between plates

Relative displacement between two composite plates was measured after different number of cycles. The measured results are presented as extensometer-displacement range, δ_{EXT} , which is the peak to peak relative displacement between the plates during the compression and tension parts of a load cycle as shown in Fig. 7(a). The obtained results for two specimens with six bolts, tested at $\sigma = 276$ MPa and 305 MPa, are shown in Fig. 7(b).

Fig. 7: Extensometer displacement: (a) nomenclature; (b) the measured results.

The extensometer curves show that changes in relative displacement between the plates occur quite early. At the beginning of fatigue loading the extensometers measured a decrease in the relative displacement between the composite plates which might be due to an increase in the coefficient of friction between the composite plates [8]. This induced an increase in the friction force between the plates, thereby causing less displacement between the plates. In addition, fatigue debris accumulated in the bolt holes could fill the clearance between the fasteners and the hole surface. This would reduce the space for the bolt to move, and as a result, the relative displacement between the plates would decrease as well.

As the number of cycles increases, the curves show a slow increase in the relative displacement between the composite plates. This is caused by the growth of fatigue damage in the bolt holes resulting in their elongation. Removal of fatigue debris from the bolt holes would create more available space for the bolts to move, thus partially resulting in the slow increase in the relative displacement between the composite plates. At the same time, the coefficient of friction could decrease due to wear of the plates [8] and the friction force decreases due to the reduction in the clamping force in the bolts. This would increase the relative displacement between the composite plates as well. The joints bolted by six fasteners failed after at least two bolts broke. In Fig. 7(b) point (a1) and (b1) reflect the first failure of bolts. As seen, this resulted in an increased relative displacement measured by that extensometer, which was attached on the same half of the specimens where the bolt failure occurred. However, in one case the second extensometer measured a drop in the relative displacement between the plates, whereas for another joint the EXT2 curve does not show any effect from the bolt failure on the extensometer measurements. Point (a2) corresponds to the second failure of a bolt, which changed the following extensometer measurements. After this, the relative displacement for the first

extensometer increased, whereas the second extensometer measured a small decrease in the relative displacement. As can be seen, even after the second bolt fractured the specimen was still able to support fatigue loading until fatigue failure of bolt No. 5.

Bolt-movement measurements

Since the joints mostly suffered from fatigue failure of bolts, it was of interest to analyse the fatigue behaviour of the fasteners under cyclic loading. Bolt-movement measurements were done on bolt No. 1 and No. 3 from specimens with four bolts (see Fig. 2(a)). One specimen with two bolts was fatigue tested with bolt-movement measurement on bolt No. 1. The obtained measurement results are presented together with the grip-displacement curves in Fig. 8 for specimens with two and four bolts, which were tested at $\sigma = 155$ MPa and 127 MPa, respectively.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 8: The measured results of bolt movement: (a) specimen with two bolts; (b) specimen with four bolts.

The grip displacement and bolt movement are characterized by three different stages of evolution. At the beginning of the fatigue tests, all curves show a decrease in the

grip displacement and bolt movement. The initial decrease has the same cause as in the extensometer curves above.

The further evolution of the grip displacement and the bolt movement is believed to be affected by reduction in pre-stress in the bolts and fatigue degradation of the bolt holes and the composite around them. The reduction in the pre-stress in the bolts results in lower friction force between the composite plates than it was at the beginning of cyclic loading. Therefore, less load is transferred between the plates by the friction force, which increases the displacement between the plates and more load being transferred by the bolts. In addition, at this stage of the fatigue tests very often accumulated fatigue debris were observed transporting out of the bolt holes by visual inspection of the specimens. Fatigue particles are caused by wear and re-deposition of composite material around the bolt holes (see Fig. 9) and bolt movement under loading [6].

Fig. 9: The middle plate of a specimen with four bolts tested at $\sigma = 166$ MPa.

Because of the removal of fatigue debris, the clearance between the fasteners and the bolt holes increased, thus inducing more movement of the bolts during fatigue loading of the specimens.

Failure of the joints with two bolts occurred after fatigue failure of one bolt; whereas the joints with four bolts failed after failure of two bolts. In Fig. 8(b) point (a1) is marked. The point corresponds to fatigue failure of bolt No. 2 (see Fig. 2(a)) after 944450 cycles. This induced more movement on bolt No. 1, but the bolt No. 3 curve shows a drop in the bolt movement after this number of cycles. Further evolution of the grip displacement and the bolt movement show a more gradual growth in the curves arising from additional damage development in the specimen, except for bolt No. 3.

Strain gauge loops

It was found that the influence of the bolt presence on the strain gauges is more pronounced for those strain gauges, which were located between two bolts (see Fig. 2). Therefore, it may be interesting to analyse the fatigue behaviour of these strain gauges as a function of number of cycles. Figure 10 shows strain gauge loops for specimens with four and six bolts. The different loops have been shifted $2000 \mu\text{strain}$ to facilitate observation. The loop arrows in the plots indicate their direction.

Fig. 10: Strain gauge loops after different number of cycles

As the plots in Fig. 10(a) and (b) show, all strain gauge loops contain some points of inflection, which are marked as (a_t) and (a_c) for the tensile and compression parts of the load cycle, respectively. These points could be a result of bolt-movement influence during cyclic loading. Due to load transfer and bolt bending, the bolts create contact forces in the area between them, i.e., the area where strain gauge No. 3 was located. The contact forces caused compressive deformation in the region between the bolts. Therefore, the strain gauge loops show an insignificant increase in strain with further loading. Moreover, the load level at which these points appear, decrease with increasing number of cycles. For example in Fig. 10(a), point (a_t) in the first loop appears at 40 kN, whereas after 4200 cycles the same point can be defined at 20 kN. It can be expected that at the beginning of the fatigue test some load is transferred by the friction force between the specimen plates. This will soften the inflection points. As fatigue loading proceeded, relaxation in the fasteners occurred, decreasing the friction force and thus inducing more load being transferred by the bolts. As a result, the bolt influence on the strain loop would occur at a lower load level within one load cycle than it was at the beginning of the fatigue test. At this stage of the fatigue test the inflection points become sharper than at its beginning.

Figure 10(c) shows strain gauge No. 8 loops for the specimen with six bolts. Analysis of the measurements found that strain gauge No. 8 behaved similar to strain gauge No. 3, especially after a large number of cycles. Despite that the hysteresis is not as pronounced as for strain gauge No. 3, its shape looks similar. However, it should be noted that the measurement on strain gauge No. 8 were done only until 4750 cycles,

when during visual inspection of the specimen two cracks in the surface ply of the composite plate were found propagating under the strain gauge, thereby causing erroneous readings.

CONCLUSIONS

Specimens with two, four, and six titanium bolts were tested in fatigue. The dominant failure mode was fatigue failure of bolts. Since for the joints with more than two bolts failure occurred after at least two bolts broke, this would not be considered indicative of catastrophic failure. Relative displacement between composite plates and bolt movement under cyclic loading are greatly affected by reduction in the pre-stress in the bolts, fatigue degradation of the composite material around the bolt holes, and fatigue elongation of the bolt holes. Strain gauge measurements between bolts showed that the bolt presence has a significant effect on the strain evolution during fatigue tests.

References

- [1] Rapoff AJ, Dill HD. Certification of damage tolerant composite structures. In: Proceedings of the Eighth DOD/NASA/FAA Conference on Fibrous Composites in Structural Design (Part 2), Langley Research Center, NASA, September 1990. p. 499–514.
- [2] Rubin AM. Common failure modes for composite aircraft structures due to secondary loads. *Composites Engineering* 1992;2(5-7):313–20.
- [3] Ashton HR. Damage tolerance and durability testing for F/A-18 E/F composite materials structures. In: Proceedings of the 37th AIAA/ASME/ASCE/AHS/ASC Structures, Structural Dynamics, and Materials Conference, Salt Lake City, UT, April 15-17 1996. p. 1–13.
- [4] Cooper C, Turvey GJ. Effects of joint geometry and bolt torque on the structural performance of single bolt tension joints in pultruded GRP sheet materials. *Composite Structures* 1995;32:217–226.
- [5] Ramkumar RL, Tossavainen EW. Strength and lifetime of bolted laminates. *Fatigue in Mechanically Fastened Composite and Metallic Joints*, ASTM STP 927, American Society for Testing and Materials, Philadelphia 1986. p. 251–273.
- [6] Saunders DS, Galea S, Deirmendsian G. The development of fatigue damage around fastener holes in thick graphite/epoxy composite laminates. *Composites* 1993;24(4):309–320.
- [7] Starikov R, Schön J. Quasi-static behaviour of composite joints with protruding-head bolts. *Composite Structures* 2001;51(4):411–425.
- [8] Schön J. Coefficient of friction of composite delamination surfaces. *Wear* 2000;237:77–89.
- [9] Saunders DS, Galea SC, Deirmendjian GK. The development of fatigue damage around fastener holes in thick graphite/epoxy composite laminates. *Composites* 1993;24(4):309–321.